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Educating for Dynamic Vocations: A Guidepost for Responsive SVET¹

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Abstract

Context: A major challenge for contemporary Secondary Vocational Education and Training (SVET) is to enhance its responsiveness. Responsiveness can be defined as the ability of (teams of) educational professionals to interpret socio-economic and technological developments for curriculum development in terms of content and pedagogical approach. In the Netherlands, SVET-qualifications are developed on a national level by tripartite stakeholders (employers, union representatives and education). Based on these national qualifications, teacher teams in the SVET-colleges have to develop curricula. Research in Dutch SVET shows that the development of SVET-curricula is often a school-internal process with a focus on planning in terms of time and sequence (Hoeve & Van Vlokhoven, 2019). Actual co-makership with business partners is still a rare phenomenon.

Approach: A consortium of six SVET-colleges and three research institutes started a collaborative interactive research project (Ellström, 2010). Interactive research is about the joint learning processes of practitioners and researchers which results in knowledge creation through co-development. The aim of the project was to develop a more interactive approach in which schools and enterprises are both actively involved in curriculum development. The central research question to be answered was: What are the characteristics of a responsive protocol that SVET teacher teams, in co-makership with their business partners, can effectively be used in the development of adaptive, vocation-oriented curricula? Representatives of 10 teacher teams participated in an inter-organisational professional learning community (iPLG). In the iPLG practitioners and researchers worked together on the design of a responsive protocol for curriculum development.

Findings: The iPLG designed a tool (guidepost) for SVET-teams to organize for responsive SVET. In the tool, two agendas are combined: an explorative agenda and a developmental agenda. The explorative agenda comprises the trends ‘outside’: the developments at the labour market and in the professional field. The developmental agenda contains the necessary curriculum components. The agendas are interrelated since developments at the occupational level should resonate in the educational programs of the SVET-college.

Conclusion: In the design of the guidepost, the significant characteristics of a responsive protocol are included. The guidepost can be used either as an analytical tool (e.g. which agenda elements are solid, which ones are we proud of; which ones need further elaboration) or as a tool to improve particular agenda items in order to increase the responsiveness of the

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curriculum. By implementing the tool in a team routine, SVET-teams will be able to monitor the quality of the responsiveness of their curriculum and make (small) adjustments on regular basis.

Keywords: responsiveness, vocational education, co-makship, curriculum development

1 Introduction

The connection between vocational education and the professional field is under pressure due to the pace of social and technological developments (see, for example, Van der Meer, 2014). Given these dynamics, there is a need for a greater degree of adaptivity in vocational education (Bussemaker, 2015; WRR, 2013; Palonen, Boshuizen, & Lehtinen, 2014). The SCP (2017) uses the term responsiveness, referring to the extent to which vocational education is able to respond adequately to changes in the labour market and to equip MBO students for a good start and permanent employability in that labour market. This requires collaboration with professionals in the field in order to be able to adapt the curricula in an adaptive way (OECD, 2014, Education Council, 2014).

Research shows that local partnership with businesses is not optimally exploited and that curriculum development is a strong school-internal process and is mainly a matter of planning in time and sequence (Hermanussen, Verheijen & Visser, 2013; Cedefop, 2012). Structural involvement of the professional field – for example through professional field committees – is not commonplace. However, there are considerable differences between domains. For example, in the Economy domain, the business community is less often involved than in the technology or care domains. Critical signals are also received from the professional field involved in local partnerships. Research into professional field committees in the construction sector shows that a majority of professional partners feel that they can contribute more by 'providing input for the program as a whole', or 'providing guest lecturers' (Kans & Van der Aa, 2013).

The need to strengthen local partnerships is recognized in a regional consortium, named the GPA, in which 6 SVET institutions and the School of Education of HAN University participate. This consortium is organized around the issue of organizing good quality and future-oriented vocational education. Research at these institutions shows that teams only make limited use of the professional field in curriculum development. It is significant to note that "...it is not organized [within the study programmes] to do anything with information from the professional field. Teachers have not been taught to deal with this: we have been in survival mode for a long time due to rigid pressure from the ministry and inspectorate," said an Economics teacher. "We haven't asked ourselves these kinds of questions in 10 years."

The inventory gives rise to a picture of a linear approach to curriculum development (see figure 1), which is confirmed by the research by Hermanussen et al. (2013). An internal school procedure for allocating competencies into learning units, in which didactic methods from external publishers are purchased in 30 % of the cases. Efficiency considerations play an important role, but the linear model leads to a connectivity problem: there is time gap between the determination of the Qualification Dossiers (QDs) and the moment students graduate. In other words, we are training for the labour market of the day after tomorrow based on knowledge of the day before yesterday (Nieuwenhuis, 2013). A second problem with the linear model is that the professional content is no longer a topic of discussion (after all, it is fixed in the QD), as a result of which the discussion between SVET-schools and the professional field mainly focuses on organizational aspects.

Figure 1

Linear model for curriculum design

The problems of this linear approach - delay and conversation focus on organizational aspects rather than content - are recognized by the GPA. There is a need for a substantiated approach to design from the outside (the work field) inwards. Dialogue with one's own regional professional field offers the opportunity to respond to developments in the regional (labour) market. The core of the desired design model is a dialogue with the regional professional field by the members of the education team who develop the curriculum. In this approach, the QD takes on more of the function of a frame of reference: interaction with the local professional field, both in the design phase and in the implementation phase, is the most important ingredient of the design process. The contours of such a more interactive model are shown in figure 2:

Figure 2

Interactive model for curriculum design

This requires a more flexible curriculum model (permeable curriculum - a curriculum with a fixed core supplemented by flexible components with current themes - de Vries 2016), different professionalism of teachers (up-to-date knowledge of developments in professional practice; more design skills to fill) and ownership and facilitation at managerial level. It requires different professional behaviour for which teacher teams should develop a professional standard (Palonen, Boshuizen, & Lehtinen, 2014). In the expertise model of Palonen et al. (2014), professional standards are stabilizing factors that support professionals in making adequate choices in complex situations. Curriculum development for rapidly changing professions is such a complex problem situation. The interactive model requires a responsive protocol, a standard of topics for the school-work field discussion and possible context-sensitive

elaborations. This project aims to develop such a protocol that supports teacher teams in making choices when developing adaptive curricula.

1.1 Problem statement and research questions

The aim of the project “Educating for dynamic vocations” is to develop a guidepost for responsive curriculum development which supports educators to be connected to developments outside, more specifically in the professional field. The usability of the guidepost will be an important quality criterion.

The central knowledge question of the project is:

What are the characteristics of a responsive protocol that SVET teacher teams, in co-makership with their business partners, can effectively be used in the development of adaptive, vocation-oriented curricula?

Based on this main question, the following sub-questions have been formulated:

- What is the current routine for curriculum development of SVET teaching teams?
- What are the building blocks (or central elements) of a responsive protocol?
- Which arguments play a role in the development and use of a responsive protocol?
- What are important preconditions for the use of a responsive protocol?

2 Method

An inter-organizational professional learning community (iPLG) was set up to answer the research questions, in which education and research professionals have jointly developed a responsive protocol. The iPLG consisted of 10 teacher-researchers from 5 SVET-institutions and 4 researchers. The teacher-researchers are the 'liaison officers' to the teaching teams. They alter between work practice and the iPLG, collect questions and feedback, monitor the relevance of practice and link (interim) outcomes back to work practice.

The research was set up as a design study in which a protocol for curriculum development is designed and tested. The design process took place in the iPLG. Theoretical, professional and practical knowledge was combined with practitioners experiences. Within the iPLG and within the SVET teacher teams social learning processes took place. (Group) Interviews and observations were used to map the quality of this interaction, both in terms of process and content (De Laat, Schreurs, & Nijland, 2014; Wenger, Trayner, & De Laat, 2011; Hanraets et al., 2011; Akkerman & Bakker, 2011; Mazereeuw et al, 2016).

3 Findings

In this section we present the main results of this research project in accordance with the sub questions of our research.

3.1 The current routine for curriculum development of SVET teaching teams

The majority of the teams regard the QD as the starting point for curriculum development and follow a linear approach. The QD serves as a guiding program for curriculum plans. Modules and assessment materials may be purchased from educational publishers. The dominant approach is inside-out reasoning: “we need so and so many internships”, and that is being organised. The discussion with the regional professional partners is often instrumental, i.e. aimed at agreements about for example work placement agreements (in terms of numbers, scope or supervision requirements). Outside in reasoning that starts with questions like what is happening in the regional work field, what developments are taking place, and how can we anticipate those developments seems to be a rare phenomenon.

Group interviews show that a majority of the teams feel that their SVET program is insufficiently connected to contemporary professional practice. Furthermore, they revealed that the

participating SVET teams are not always aware of their current routine for curriculum development. A striking finding was that all teams involved indicated that they actually do not have a clear working method. In many teams, curriculum (re)design is the responsibility of a small group of assigned persons. However, the fact that many teams opt for this construction does not automatically mean that they think this is a good way of working. Some of the participating members criticized this approach as being a weakness in their current way of working.

It is a real challenge for most teams to reason from the outside in. It requires a culture change from the teaching team (and the organization).

3.2 Building blocks for a responsive protocol

In order to adequately respond to developments in the (regional) professional field, it is necessary for teams to keep in touch with the dynamics in their region and to be able to translate them into the study curriculum. Yet, teams find this a very difficult task. Like any task that requires collective action from different stakeholders, it is important to build common ground by developing a shared vision on:

- Professional image and work processes. For which profession(s) is/are being trained? And what are the professional tasks within that profession?
- Developments in the profession: What changes and innovations are taking place in/around the profession nationally and in the region and what consequences does this have for the training?
- Learning from novice, via starting competence to competence: roughly what is the route from the status of novice/newcomer in the field to starting competence and competence? Up to what level can the training guide the student and where do social partners themselves take over this process?
- Assessing professional competence: how can the development of professional competence be assessed?

For each of these items, the question is whether there is a shared vision on the particularly item, i.e. sufficiently shared among team members and their professional partners. In doing so, the team always asks itself whether its shared insights are up to date. Documents from SBB (the QD and the trend reports) are important resources and frames of reference for this, in addition to our own observations in the field.

Looking from a value-creation perspective, professions or vocations change much less rapidly than looking from the level of tasks and techniques. In line with Gessler and Höwe (2015), we follow this distinction and thereby differentiate between spheres of work and tasks of work. The spheres of work form the robust core of the profession and are much less changeable than the tasks of work. The latter is directly influenced by social, technological, organisational and product developments and is much more changeable. The tasks of work can easily be adapted intermediately to regional work field developments. A responsive vocational curriculum, therefore, takes into account both the robust spheres and changing tasks; together, they can offer a way out of the problem of an unknown future labour market. In addition, this unknown future requires free space in the curriculum to be able to respond to new (regional) developments and to provide room for the development of the self-regulating capacity of future professionals. Miller calls this "future's literacy" (2013); learning to deal with uncertainties in work and preparing for lifelong development. Adaptivity, agility and self-regulation are important characteristics (or terms of development).

In this line of reasoning the iPLG identified the following building blocks for curriculum development:

- Constant and changeable elements in the curriculum: Which elements in the profession are constant and which elements can be flexibly filled in and continuously adapted?

- Learning environments; workplace learning and hybrid forms: What are appropriate learning environments for the different professional tasks?
- Assessment and evaluation in co-makship: With whom, when, what and how is professional competence assessed?
- Determining the structure of the curriculum or parts of it: In what order (sequence) should someone learn parts of the profession? To what extent is that structure flexible and is there a choice for students?

Development of self-direction: How does the student learn to steer his own professional development and deal with developments in the profession?

Based on the elements of shared vision making and curriculum development, the iPLG designed a guidepost for SVET-teams to organize for responsive SVET. In the tool, two agendas are combined: an explorative agenda and a developmental agenda (See table 1). The explorative agenda comprises the trends ‘outside’, the developments at the labour market and in the professional field. The developmental agenda contains the necessary curriculum components. The agendas are interrelated since developments at the occupational level should resonate in the educational programs of the SVET-college.

Every agenda item of the explorative agenda consists of an objective (what is the rationale of this item) and is devised into different investigating questions to be answered in collaboration with the occupational partners. In addition, potential risks are described when the agenda item is not in the picture of the SVET-team. The developmental agenda has the same kind of structure, although not all the items might be answered in dialogue with stakeholders from the labour market.

Table 1

Elements of the explorative and the developmental agenda

Explorative agenda	Developmental agenda
Developments in the professional field	Learning environments – workplace learning-hybrid designs
Learning: novice - competent - proficient	Stable and dynamic elements
Occupational profile & work processes	Training of self-regulation
Assessment of expertise development	Structure and sequence of the curriculum
	Valuation and assessment

The guidepost can be used either as an analytical tool (e.g. which agenda elements are solid, which ones are we proud of, which ones need further elaboration) or as a tool to improve particular agenda items in order to increase the responsiveness of the curriculum. By implementing the tool in a team routine, SVET-teams will be able to monitor the quality of the responsiveness of their curriculum and make (small) adjustments on regular basis.

3.3 Which Arguments Play a Role in the Development and Use of a Responsive Protocol?

Collaboration with educational practice in this project made clear that the urgency and effort of teachers is foremost on (organising) student learning and much less on a more abstract task of curriculum (re)development. In the hectic of everyday educational practice, it also appears difficult to make time and mental space for curriculum (re)design processes. Time and focus on curriculum development issues are mostly restricted to planned moments and usually with a specific assignment. A responsive curriculum as a continuous process with the active involvement of the professional field is not common practice at all. On the one hand, this is due

to the lack of time and mental space experienced by teacher teams. Their focus and energy are primarily directed at the professional development of their students and the daily issues involved (such as administration). It also has to do with the way teams perceive their task. Do they consider it their task to (continuously) engage in responsive dialogue with partners in the field? And is this task also fostered by the organisation? Is it a task entrusted to the teams or to specific people for example? In this project, we noticed that although the lines of communication with the professional field of work are always in place, but mostly flimsy organised. Sometimes they even depend on certain people. Most teams seem to lack a well-thought-out working method with which the developments from 'outside' are systematically translated into the curriculum. The linear approach is a safe and generally accepted choice.

Another insight from this project is that a curriculum design seems to be regarded by teachers as an implementation plan. In terms of the curriculum concept of Thijs and Van den Akker (2009), the focus of teachers seems to be on the "implemented" curriculum and less on the "intended" curriculum. This hindered the design process in the iPLG from time to time, as practitioners did not always feel comfortable and equipped for the abstract decisions about developing a generic tool that can be applied in different contexts. Continuously switching between the perspectives of a generic tool and their own daily practice, especially when the student seems to be out of sight, is not easy. While a responsive curriculum and its development require the constant shifting between these perspectives. With the two different agendas that the Guidepost comprises, the exploration agenda and the development agenda, we have tried to meet this need.

3.4 Preconditions for the use of a responsive protocol

As mentioned above, teacher teams still have little routine for jointly and systematically translating 'outside' developments into their curriculum. The experiences in this project show that models of curriculum design in consultation with professional partners do work at the national level (as laid down in KDs) but not at the local level where the teacher teams should be in the lead. Part of the reason is that at the local level, ownership is somewhat lacking; teachers foremost feel responsible for the student. Only when the student encounters obstacles related to a lack of responsiveness do they feel the need to change this.

Another explanation is that responsive curriculum development requires the development of a different kind of professionalism. In the first place, it requires design knowledge and/or experience to ensure that teacher teams feel sufficiently equipped to take the lead in curriculum development (instead of leaving it to curriculum coaches or other designated experts).

In addition, the composition of teams must guarantee a mix of expertise, with an eye for the necessary expertise regarding:

- Current, (professional) content knowledge about the issue/theme/subject.
- Specific, current practical experience/field of work
- Knowledge/experience (current) education: how are we doing? What are our strengths/problems (see product 1. discussion of thesis)

The development of a robust team routine on responsive curriculum development naturally takes time, access to budget (for professionalisation) and support. Teams unanimously indicate a lack of enough support. Here it is good to realise that the call for support and resources is not always meant literally. It is often more about the mental space needed to come up with creative ideas and experiments. It is striking that the national KD is not really experienced as an obstacle for local creative ideas and experiments.

4 Conclusions

In the design of the guidepost, the significant characteristics of a responsive protocol are included, which will answer the central research question. In the tool, two agendas are combined: an explorative agenda and a developmental agenda. The explorative agenda comprises the trends ‘outside’, the developments in the labour market and in the professional field. The developmental agenda contains the necessary curriculum components. The agendas are inter-related since developments at the occupational level should resonate in the educational programs of the SVET-college.

However, the main insight of the project might be that professionals need qualified space to anticipate adequately on continuous uncertainty. This implies a perspective shift from controllability towards acceptance of a kind of uncertainty somehow. SVET-professionals are looking for a balance between insecurity and security, between robust and volatile/ dynamic aspects of the curriculum. In line with the distinction between ‘spheres and tasks of work’ (Gessler & Howe, 2015) we detected two processes that should be constantly balanced: declining uncertainty as well as stretching the professional space of professionals. The guidepost is a tool for SVET teams to support them in balancing these two processes.

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Biographical notes

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